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AN EXAMINATION OF THE JURISDICTION AND COMPETENCE OF THE FEDERAL AND STATES HIGH COURTS OVER ISLAMIC BANKING DISPUTES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

As Islamic banking booms in Nigeria, disputes become inevitable. While litigation is the eventual way of resolving disputes, there is controversy as to which court in Nigeria has jurisdiction and competence to adjudicate Islamic banking matters. Section 251 (1) (d) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) bestows exclusive jurisdiction over banking and related matters in the Federal High Court and concurrent jurisdiction in the Federal and State High Courts in banker-customer related matters. Questions whether Islamic banking falls within the purview of section 251(1) (d) and whether the Federal and States High Courts are qualified to preside over Islamic banking matters remain unanswered.

The objectives of this research are to investigate and explain whether the Federal and State High Courts have jurisdiction, qualification and competence to adjudicate Islamic banking matters in Nigeria. Using adjudication, realists, and competence theories, the research would explain how and what the courts in Nigeria do when adjudicating Islamic banking matters. The researcher uses the doctrinal methodology of research to investigate if the Constitution and other Nigerian laws bestow in the Federal and States High Courts jurisdiction and competence over Islamic banking matters. The research finds that no Nigerian court is expressly clothed with jurisdiction and competence over Islamic banking matters and that Judges of the Federal and States High Courts are not required by any law to be knowledgeable in Islamic law and are therefore incompetent to administer justice to litigants in Islamic banking matters.

Keywords: *Jurisdiction, Competence, Disputes, Interest Free, Profit and Loss Sharing and Islamic Banking.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, more than 250 Islamic financial institutions are operating in over 50 countries worldwide.¹ Islamic banking in Nigeria is rapidly growing. Starting from Islamic banking windows in 1999 to full-fledged Islamic banks - Jaiz Bank Plc, Taj Bank Limited and recently Lotus bank Limited. Islamic banking is a banking system which complies with Islamic law and based on *Fiqhul Mu'amalaat*. Islamic banking offers special products such as *Mudarabah*, *musharakah*, *ijarah*, *wadiah* and disputes often arise in the course of such transactions.

Disputes may be resolved through litigation which appears to be the most effective, viable and binding means of resolving disputes or by way of any of the Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms. Though courts play the most effective role in resolving Islamic banking disputes and despite the provision of Section 251 (1) (d) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999), there is controversy as to whether the Federal and States High Courts in Nigeria have jurisdiction and competence to adjudicate Islamic banking matters. Questions whether Islamic banking falls within the purview of section 251(1) (d) and whether Judges of the Federal and States High Court are qualified and competent to preside over Islamic banking matters remain unanswered.

Using adjudication, realists, and competence theories, this paper would investigate and explain whether the Federal and State High Courts have jurisdiction, qualification and competence to adjudicate Islamic banking matters in Nigeria. It would explain how and what the courts in Nigeria do and what is expected of them when adjudicating Islamic banking matters and using the doctrinal methodology. The paper would investigate if the Constitution and other laws bestow in the Federal and States High Courts, jurisdiction over Islamic banking matters. The research finds that no Nigerian court is expressly clothed with jurisdiction over Islamic banking matters and that Judges of the Federal and States High Courts are not required by law to be knowledgeable in Islamic law. The paper also finds that judges of the Federal and State High Courts are incompetent to administer justice to litigants in Islamic banking matters.

2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Islamic banking is a special kind of banking governed strictly by Islamic laws of transaction as distinct from conventional Nigerian Laws and therefore adjudication over disputes emanating

¹Nuruddeen A.A. (2016) "Islamic Banking in Nigeria: issues and prospects", *Journal of Emerging Economies and Islamic Research* Vol 4 No. 4 <https://www.jeeir.com> Accessed on 9/12/2023

from Islamic banking transactions require knowledgeable and competent adjudicators. While sections 251 (1) (d), 257 (1) and 272 (1) of the Constitution specifically saddle Federal and States High Courts with jurisdiction over banking matters, no express provision in that regard is made in respect of Islamic banking matters and qualification of judges of such courts seem to fall short. Therefore, there is controversy as to whether the Federal and States High Courts in Nigeria have jurisdiction and competence to adjudicate Islamic banking matters.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

The objectives of this research are to investigate and explain whether the Federal and State High Courts have jurisdiction, qualification and competence to adjudicate Islamic banking matters in Nigeria. Using adjudication, realists and competence theories, the research would explain how and what the courts in Nigeria do when adjudicating Islamic banking matters.

4. METHODOLOGY

The paper uses the doctrinal methodology of research by which the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and other Nigerian legislations as well as decided cases are examined to determine whether the Federal and States High Courts have jurisdiction and competence over Islamic banking matters.

5. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Several theories have been used to examine jurisdiction and competence of courts. The research would use the theory of adjudication² to examine how and what the courts in Nigeria do while adjudicating over Islamic banking matters under the current legal regime and to find out whether the courts in Nigeria are required to preside over Islamic banking cases.

The Islamic legal theory of *Usul-al- Fiqh*³ has set the standard and it has been used to explain the qualifications a person must possess before he could be competent to adjudicate Islamic law matters. This paper would use the theory to determine whether Nigerian judges are competent and qualified in law and in practice to adjudicate Islamic banking matters.

² Provides an accurate description of how judges really do decide cases and, at the same time strives to tell judges how they ought to decide cases.

³ Formulates general jurisprudential rules addressing the way and manner Islamic law is derived, hierarchy of the sources of Islamic law, interpretation and application of Islamic Law as well as providing as an integral legal methodology, legal interpretations, analogies and deductions in the administration of Islamic justice.

Competence theory which postulates that competence develops through a combination of experience, knowledge, practice and feedback tied to an individual's sense of efficacy or belief in their ability to perform in a given domain would be used to identify and analyze the necessary knowledge, skills and motivation that judges need to have to understand the principles and legal rulings of Islamic banking and apply them in resolving disputes that may arise in the course of business.

The paper shall use the theoretical tools to understand how existing literature define the concepts of jurisdiction, competence, justice and disputes in the general context and see how they relate to adjudication in Islamic banking matters in Nigeria.

In its conventional sense, jurisdiction is said to be a concept distinct and different from the merits of a case. The US Supreme Court⁴ explained that jurisdiction is the power of court to entertain and preside over a case *simpliciter* as distinct from the ability of the court to arrive at a right and just decision. Justice Holmes opines that our legal culture insists that power is the essential quality making jurisdiction unique and the foundation of jurisdiction is physical power.⁵ Jurisdiction is simply whether the court has the power to proceed to other questions (in a given suit) and in its absence, the court's only function is to dismiss the case.⁶ Thus, the Nigeria's Supreme Court in *Shell Petroleum Development Company Nigeria Ltd v. Isaiah (2001)* describes Jurisdiction as the "...fulcrum, center-pin or the main pillar upon which the validity of any decision of any court stands and around which other issues rotate, lack of which renders any decision reached a nullity."⁷ By this conceptualization, jurisdiction is the statutory powers conferred on courts to preside over given matters which implies that if the court possesses jurisdiction, its judgment on the merits will be binding even if the court has reached the wrong result by way of seriously flawed process and if it otherwise lacks jurisdiction, the decision would be invalid, void and of no effect nor matter how sound, right and just the decision might be.

From normative perspective, the Halsbrury's Laws of England⁸ defines jurisdiction as the authority which a court has to take cognizance or decide matters litigated before it as granted

⁴ *Steel Co. v. Citizens for a Better Env't*, 523 U.S. 83, 94 (1998).

⁵ *McDonald v. Mabee*, 243 U.S. 90,91 (1915).

⁶ *United States v. Cotton*, 535 U.S. 625 (2002), *overruling Ex parte Bain*, 121 U.S. 1 (1887) ("*Bain's* elastic concept of jurisdiction is not what the term 'jurisdiction' means today, *i.e.*, 'the courts' statutory or constitutional power to adjudicate the case") (quoting *Steel Co.*, 523 U.S. at 89);

⁷ See also *GTB v. Toyed (Nig) Ltd & Anor* (2016) 7 (2016) LPELR-4181 (CA)

⁸ (5th Ed. 2010) Vol. 24

by statute. The US Supreme Court in *Rhode Island v. Massachusetts*,⁹ concurs and defines jurisdiction as both "power" and "authority" of a court to hear and determine the subject matter in controversy between parties to a suit. In this perspective, Jurisdiction is referred to as the combination of power and authority.¹⁰ Thus, the Supreme Court of Nigeria in *Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited v. Lagos State Environmental Protection Agency & Ors*, (2002) 12 S.C (Pt. I) 26 defines jurisdiction "...as the authority, which a court has to decide matters that are litigated before it or take cognizance of matters presented in a formal way for its decision."

In the *locus classicus Madukolu v. Nkemdilim*¹¹ the Supreme Court expanded the concept of jurisdiction to mean a situation when a court is properly constituted with respect to number and qualifications of its members; the subject-matter of the action being within the jurisdiction of the court; and the action initiated by due process of the law. Recently, in *Inajoku V. Adeleke*¹² Niki Tobi supports this position when he describes jurisdiction as a radical and crucial question of competence of the court to validly entertain and adjudicate over matters brought before it. This definition extends the conceptualization to include qualification of the judge and quorum to sit over a given matter as well as fulfilling any conditions precedents.

The conceptualization in *Madukolu v. Nkemdilim* has been criticized that it has failed to distinguish between the existence of jurisdiction, exercise of jurisdiction and competence of court to exercise jurisdiction. Proponents of this criticism argue that, the concept of jurisdiction can be best defined when aligned to first or root principles of English law on jurisdiction which states that judges stand in place of the sovereign in whose name they administer justice¹³ and that jurisdiction of a court is analogous to the judicial function of the sovereign power of the state, hence, a court only truly lacks jurisdiction if it lacks authority to adjudicate over the subject matter of the dispute. In all other cases, the court has jurisdiction, but through the exercise of its jurisdiction, in line with statute or its rules, may decide not to exercise such jurisdiction.¹⁴

In Islamic law, jurisdiction of court entails the knowledge, expertise and trustworthiness of the judge such that if the judge is not knowledgeable in law or cannot deliver justice to the parties

9 37 U.S. (12 Pet.) 657, 718 (1838),

¹⁰ *GTB v. Toyed (Nig) Ltd & Anor* (2016)¹⁰ (2016) LPELR-4181 (CA). (Supra)

¹¹ (1962) 1 ALL NLR (Pt. 4) 557, Per Baramian JSC.

¹² (2007) 4 NWLR (Pt. 1025) 423

¹³ Aziz O.R. (Sept 2016) "Rethinking Jurisdiction under the Nigerian Legal System: Need for Realignment to First Principles" *Gravitas Review of Business & Property Law*, Vol. 7, No. 3 p. 16

¹⁴ *John Russels & Co. V Carper, Irvine & Co.* (1916) 2 AC 298

or has some sort of interest or in any way impaired to do justice to the parties, the court would lack jurisdiction.¹⁵

For the purpose of this work, jurisdiction is the power, authority, academic qualification and competence to find, understand and interpret Islamic legal provisions in consonance with the principles of *maqasid-al Sharia*. This paper contends that jurisdiction entails not only the powers and authority of courts to entertain, hear and determine cases brought before them but also the academic and professional qualifications and competence of the judges as prescribed by the Constitution.

The concept of dispute, from the general perspective, is defined as divergence of interest or a belief that the parties' current aspirations cannot be achieved simultaneously.¹⁶ Thus, traditionally, dispute (conflict) is thought to arise from opposing interests involving scarce resources and goal divergence and frustration.¹⁷ In its restrictive sense, dispute is defined as "perceived incompatibilities or discrepant views among the parties involved"¹⁸ In this sense, dispute means a sort of misunderstanding or inability of parties to a given transaction to come to terms and agree on their respective interests in the transaction.

From legal perspective, dispute is any disagreements, arguments or controversies that give rise to a legal proceeding(s) such as arbitration, mediation or a law suit.¹⁹ The International Court of Justice defines dispute as "a disagreement on a point of law or fact or conflict of legal views or of interests between two parties."²⁰ In another case, the ICJ describes dispute as "a situation where the two sides held clearly opposite views concerning questions of performance or non-performance of a treaty or an obligation."²¹ By this definition, for any disagreement to amount to a dispute, the disagreement must be of law or of fact bordering on performance or non-performance of an obligation by either party. These definitions however restrict the disagreement to be between two parties when in reality disagreements may be between two or more parties to a transaction.

15 Abdullahi S.I. 2010 Islamic Banking in Nigeria: Issues and Prospects CBN Bullion. 34(2), 36-42

16 Rubin J.Z. (1994) Social Conflict: Escalation, Stalemate and Settlement McGraw Hill, New York (2nd Ed.)

¹⁷ Mack, R.W. and Snyder, R.C. (1957), "The analysis of social conflict – toward an overview and synthesis", *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, Vol. 1, pp. 212-48.

¹⁸ Jehn, K.A. & Bendersky, C. (2003), "Intragroup conflict in organizations: a contingency perspective on the conflict-outcome relationship", *Research in Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 25, pp. 187-242.

¹⁹ Black's Law Dictionary 7th Ed. See also www.law.cornell.edu/wex/dispute. Accessed on 8/12/2023

20 See the case of Mavrommatis Palestine Concessions Judgment No. 2, 1924, P.C.I.J., Series A, No. 2, p 11.

21 Interpretation of the Peace Treaty with Bulgaria, Hungary and Romania (First Phase) ICJ Reports 1950 pp. 5

In this work, dispute is conceptualized to mean any disagreement, argument or controversy on a point of law or fact or conflict of legal views or of interests of parties or as to performance or non-performance of an obligation or breach of right that give rise to a legal proceeding (s) between parties to a given transaction.

6. NATURE, PRINCIPLES AND PRACTICE OF ISLAMIC BANKING IN NIGERIA

The Central Bank of Nigeria being the official government institution saddled with the responsibility of regulating and supervising the affairs of all banks in Nigeria, describes Islamic bank as “a bank or other Financial Institution (OFI) under the purview of the Central Bank (CBN), which transacts banking business, engages in trading, investment and commercial activities as well as the provision of financial products and services in accordance with *Sharia* principles and rules of Islamic commercial jurisprudence.²² Islamic banking business therefore refers to that banking system which complies with the precepts, prescriptions and objectives of Islamic law to safeguard the lives, welfare, faith, wealth and well-being of the people.²³

Islamic banking is fashioned in accordance with the rules of *Sharia*, known as *Fiqh al-Muamalat* (Islamic rules on transactions) and operates based on five major tenets of prohibition of *ribah*, *gharar*, the derivation of money on money, avoidance of *haram* activities and operating based on the principle of profit and loss sharing.²⁴ In compliance with these principles, Islamic banks do not engage in many conventional banking transactions which are tainted with one or all of the forbidden elements.

To sustain their competitive advantage against conventional banks, Islamic banks engage in alternative practices and offer products and services that covers up the gap created by the forbidden transactions such as *Mudarabah*, *Musharakah*, *Kafalah*, *Rahn*, *Wadi'ah*, *Wakalah*, *Hiwalah*, *Muqasah Murabahah*, *Musawamah* and *Ijarah* among others which conventional banks do not offer.

22 Guidelines for the regulation and supervision of institutions offering non-interest financial service in Nigeria, 2016

23 Nasiru A. Ahmad & Mansur Idris (2015) Principles and Practice of Islamic Banking Benchmark Publishers Limited Kano

24 *Elfakhani S.M., Zbib I.J. and Ahmed Z.U.* (Marketing of Islamic financial products) “*Handbook of Islamic banking*” Edward Elgar (Ed.) (Edward Elgar publishing limited Gtensandu House Montpellier parade) Cheltenham UK. Pp 116-127

The historical development of Islamic banking in Nigeria dates back to 1990s when the idea was first mooted. In 1992, two licenses were granted to two banks to operate Non-interest Banking which could not commence operation until 1999 when Habib Nigeria Bank Limited started a non-interest banking window. The promulgation of the Banks and other financial institutions Decree (BOFID) 1991 ushered a new dawn for banking operations and by extension Islamic Banking in Nigeria²⁵. In 2011 the CBN New Banking Model authorizes the establishment of Commercial Banks, Merchant Banks and Specialized Banks under which non-interest banks, microfinance banks, development banks; mortgage banks are designated. It was pursuant to this that on 11th November, 2011, the Central Bank of Nigeria granted an approval to Jaiz Bank to operate an interest-free bank in Nigeria thereby becoming the first full-fledged Islamic Bank in Nigeria followed by Taj Bank on 17th July, 2019 and in June, 2021 and most recently Lotus bank.²⁶

Islamic commercial law sets certain principles as guiding tools for Islamic banking. One of the essential principles of Islamic banking is that all transactions must comply with the laid down ethical rules and principles of Islamic commercial law which prohibits all forms of transactions that tend to take undue advantage of one party in favour of the other such as the payment or collection of *Riba*, dealing in *Maysir*, and *gharar*. *Ribah* is the premium, increase, growth or any predetermined excess in which no counter value is given²⁷ that the borrower must pay to the lender on top of the principal,²⁸ it is prohibited in the *Quran* in four separate revelations²⁹ and stages.

Ribah is of two forms - *Ribah*-in-debt; and *Ribah*-in-exchange (*riba al nasiah*; *riba al fadl*). While *Riba al nasiah* occurs when the specified increase is in return for postponement of, or waiting for, the payment, *Riba al fadl* occurs when the increase mentioned is irrespective of the postponement and is not offset by something in return.³⁰ The two are strictly prohibited by Islamic Law as they both contravene the cardinal objective of Islamic banking which is based

25 Mustapha D., Ibrahim M.Y. & Adewale A. (May, 2011) "The establishment and operation of Islamic Banks in Nigeria: perception Study on the role of the Central Bank of Nigeria", " *Australian Journal of Business and Management* " Research Vol.1 No.2

26 www.lotusbank.com Accessed on 20/11/2023.

27 Ayub Muhammad, (2007) *Understanding Islamic Finance*, <https://books.google.com.ng/books>.

28 Edward Elgar (2007) "*Handbook of Islamic banking*" (Edward Elgar publishing limited Gtensandu House Montpellier parade)

29 Surah al-Rum Chapter 30, verse 39; Surah al-Nisa Chapter 39, verse 161; Surah al-Imran Chapter 3, verses 130-2; and Surah al-Baqarah Chapter 2, verses 275-81.

30 Abdullahi S.I. 2010 *Islamic Banking in Nigeria: Issues and Prospects* CBN Bullion. 34(2), 36-42

on the ethical principles of social justice, equality, property rights, fairness, transparency and integrity.

Islamic law prohibits of *gharar* so Islamic banks do not engage in it. *Gharar* means uncertainty and/or ignorance of one or both parties in a contract over the substance or the attributes of the object of sale or doubt over its existence or availability at the time of the contract which should be avoided in commercial exchange contracts. However, some degree of *gharar* or uncertainty is acceptable in the Islamic framework in four different instances³¹ like where it is minor; where the contract is unilateral or charitable such as a gift or bequest, such that the other party is not exploited; where there is public need or interest in the contract; or where risk is inherent in the productive economic activities.

Islamic banks are prohibited from engaging in transaction involving *Maysir* which means gambling³² or pure games of chance whose outcome is uncertain and accrues profit without any economic efforts; sale of intoxicants, dead meat, swine, idols, prostitution, unjust enrichment, exploitation and unfair trade practices, dealing in pork, arms and ammunitions, pornography and dealing in other transactions, products, goods or services which are not in compliance with the rules and principles of Islamic commercial jurisprudence.

Islamic banking adopts the principles of profit and loss sharing and debt-based contracts as two basic means of transacting business between the bank and its customers in *Mudharabah*,³³ *Wadiah*,³⁴ *Musharakah*³⁵, *Wakalah*,³⁶ *Murabahah*³⁷ and *Ijara, istisna, and bai' asalam*. Profit and Loss Sharing (PLS) is a system of Islamic finance by which parties in a transaction jointly pool in their resources for business purposes and agree to share in profit, risk and losses in the ratio of their individual capital input thereby ensuring no accrual of a fixed interest to either

31 El-Gamal M. (2006) *Islamic Finance: Law, Economics and Practice* (Cambridge,) USA

32 El-Gamal M.A. *Islamic Finance: Law, Economics and Practice*, Cambridge University Press 2006

33 An Islamic finance technique in which a lender and borrower establish a profit-sharing partnership to undertake a business activity.

34 Deposit of funds or assets by a person with an Islamic bank for safe keeping and in most agreements the bank charges a fee for safe custody of the said funds or assets

35 An agreement between two or more parties to combine their assets, labour or liabilities for the purpose of making profit

36 An agency contract, where one party appoints another to conduct a defined legal action on his behalf, for a specified fee or commission which applies in Islamic banking business when the investor deposits his funds with the agent (the bank) and the agent invests the funds deposited by the investor in a pool and remits returns inform of profit or loss to the investor.

37 Sale of a commodity at a price that includes a set profit of which both the vendor (marketer) and the consumer are aware as the customer is normally appointed as agent of the bank for purchase of the item on its behalf.

party³⁸. Islamic banks use the system to comply with the religious prohibition on interests on loans.³⁹ PLS therefore is a mechanism of banking and finance activity that is consistent with the principles of the Sharia which seeks for the redistribution of resources amongst investors and stands against oppression and all forms of illegalities.⁴⁰

PLS is practiced in Islamic banking products by way of *sharikah*. The principle of *sharika* is practiced in *Mudarabah* in which the *rabbul mal* provides capital and the other party- *mudarib* provides labour and profit is shared between the parties at a mutually agreed ratio and in case of a loss, it will be borne by the capital provider and the *mudarib* will lose his efforts.

Disputes often arise out of transactions in the products offered by Islamic bank, the most common of which are disputes that may require the court to determine the compliance or non-compliance of the given transaction to Islamic banking principles which involves disagreements regarding whether the bank's practices and transactions comply with Islamic principles and the guidelines set by Islamic law. This may involve questions about the legitimacy of certain investments or the permissibility of certain transactions. Also, Disputes related to profit-sharing in investment accounts or profit-sharing investment contracts that would require the calculation and distribution of profits. Disputes pertaining to the default of loans or failure to fulfill financial obligations which may involve disputes over the enforcement of collateral, calculation of penalties, or the process of debt collection and recovery.

Also, disputes arising out of breach of *Musharakah*, *Mudarabah*, *Ijarah* or other forms of agreements, interpretations of terms of contracts and banking products arising as to the construction and interpretation of Islamic legal rulings and contract agreements in *Mudarabah*, *Musharakah*, *Murabahah*, *Ijarah*, *Bai'as Salam*, *Istisna'* and other related transactions such as Sales Contract (*Aqd Al-Bay*), loan contract (*aqd al-qard*), lease contract (*aqd al-ijar*), partnerships (*al-sharikat*), agency contract (*aqd- al-wakalah*), investment contracts, pawning and mortgage (*Al-Rahn*). Engaging in *gharar* as well as other transactions that are prone to misunderstandings results in disputes that would require the court to determine the nature of the *gharar* and decide whether or not it affects the transaction. These and many more disputes are purely governed by the Islamic financial laws at which the judges are neither

38O. C. Paul & O. N. Osmond (2016) The Principles of Islamic Banking and the Nigerian Business Environment *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 4(1):46-56,

39 Ahmad T. A. (2011) "Islamic Banking and prohibition of interest" *African journal of Business Management*. Vol. 5(5), 1763-1767.

⁴⁰ Khaf, M. (1996) Profit Distribution in Islamic Banks. *Review of Islamic Economic Studies* Vol.3 No.2, 130.

knowledgeable, trained nor required to be so. Effective resolution of these disputes requires an in-dept and thorough knowledge of the existing substantive Islamic legal rules and principles as well as procedural postulations that are to be used to apply the legal rules in relevant circumstances on the part of the judge.

7. JURISDICTION AND COMPETENCE OF THE FEDERAL HIGH COURT OVER ISLAMIC BANKING DISPUTES

The administration of justice⁴¹ is the primary responsibility of courts.⁴² As the 1999 Constitution prescribes the jurisdiction of each court,⁴³ section 251 (1) (d) of the Constitution vests in the Federal High Court exclusive jurisdiction in civil causes and matters connected with or pertaining to banking, banks, other financial institutions, including any action between one bank and another, any action by or against the Central Bank of Nigeria arising from banking, foreign exchange, coinage, legal tender, bills of exchange, letters of credit, promissory notes and other fiscal measures with the exception of any dispute between an individual customer and his bank in respect of transactions between the individual customer and the bank. The Supreme Court of Nigeria reviewed the jurisdiction of the Federal High Court in the case of *NDIC v. Okem Enterprises Ltd* (2004) 10 NWLR (Pt. 880) 107 and concluded that the 1999 Constitution has now conferred wider jurisdiction on the Federal High Court to the exclusion of other courts, hence all the previous case law delimiting the jurisdiction of the Federal High Court on the matters now clearly set under section 251 (1) of the 1999 Constitution are now spent forces and that only the Federal High Court now has exclusive jurisdiction over all matters preceding the proviso under subsection (1) (d); and that both State High Court and Federal High Court now have concurrent jurisdiction in claims between individual customers and their banks in respect of banking transactions.

While section 7 of the Federal High Court Act rehashes the provision of section 251 of the Constitution and section 252 (1) of the Constitution provides that for the purpose of excising any jurisdiction conferred upon it by this Constitution or as may be conferred by an Act of the National Assembly, the Federal High Court shall have all the powers of the High Court of a

41 Interpreting and applying the rule of law

42 *Anozia v. Attorney General of Lagos State* (2010) 15 NWLR (Pt. 1216) 207 at 237. See also Section 6 (1), (2) and (6) of the 1999 Constitution.

43 While the 1999 Constitution prescribes subject matter jurisdiction, rules of courts and practice directions of various courts often provide for jurisdiction with reference to the formalities for the commencement, maintaining and prosecuting suits before the court.

state. The Court in *Olubeko V FRN*⁴⁴ held that section 251 (2) does not confer jurisdiction of the State High Court in the Federal High Court but that the wording of section 252(1) is very clear, plain and unambiguous to the effect that it is only for the purpose of exercising any jurisdiction conferred upon it by the Constitution or any Act of the National Assembly that a Federal High Court shall be clothed with the power of a state High Court.

Does Islamic banking fall within the realm of banking mentioned in paragraph (d) of section 251 of the Constitution? Can the Federal High Court exercise jurisdiction over Islamic banking matters pursuant to section 251 (d) of the 1999 Constitution? In one realm, it has been argued that Islamic banking falls within the realm of banking mentioned in paragraph (d) over which the Federal High Court can exercise jurisdiction because by the provisions of section 131 of the BOFIA 2020, Islamic banking falls within the class of banking business in Nigeria as it offers and engage in all the businesses and products mentioned in the section and that the section did not expressly exclude Islamic banking as a form of banking in Nigeria.

It is further argued that the CBN's new banking model 2011 classified Islamic banking under specialized banks, for the regulation of which the CBN developed guidelines and that section 251(1) (d) makes a general provision over all banks and did not expressly exclude Islamic banking from the jurisdiction of the Federal High Court as did sections 262(1) and 277 (1) of the Constitution. Therefore, if the drafters of the Constitution had intended to exclude Islamic banking from the purview of section 251 (d), they could have stated so expressly.

In another perspective, it is argued that section 251(1) (d) vested in the Federal High Court exclusive jurisdiction over conventional banking only and since Islamic banking is distinct and different from conventional banking, the Federal High Court cannot have proper and actual jurisdiction over Islamic banking more so that neither section 251 of the Constitution, 28(3) of the Constitution (First Alteration) Act 2010, 7(9) and 28 of the Federal High Court Act 2004 nor any other statute expressly mention Islamic banking as within the jurisdiction of the Federal High Court. That going by the principles in *Expressio Unus Est Exclusio Alterius*, it is a cardinal principle of construction of statutory provisions that where a statute specifically mentions things or persons, it is the intention of the legislators that those not mentioned are intended to be excluded as enunciated by the Supreme Court in the case of *Udoh V Orthopaedic Hospital Management Board*.⁴⁵

44 (2014) LPELR – CA/L/121/2011

45 (1993) 7 NWLR (Pt. 304) 139. See also *Ogbuanyinya V Okudo* (1979) 6-9 SC 32

It is further contended that neither the Constitution nor any other statute mandates the Federal High Court judges to be learned in Islamic law as part of requirements for their qualification. Thus, if the drafters of the Constitution intend or even contemplate vesting the Federal High Court with jurisdiction over Islamic banking disputes, they would have made it a requirement.

Judges are saddled with the responsibilities of determining disagreements on a point of law or fact or conflict of legal views or of interests between two parties to any given Islamic banking transaction, the compliance or non-compliance of Islamic banking transactions with Islamic legal principles, breach or violation of terms of Islamic contracts and other conflicts that may arise between parties. To be competent, the judges are expected to have deep knowledge and training in Islamic banking law upon which the contracts, transaction and banking products are offered and agreed upon by parties.

To determine the competence of the Federal High Court to adjudicate Islamic banking disputes, reference shall be made to competence theory which postulates that knowledge and experience determines competence to find out if judges of the Federal High Court knowledgeable or trained in Islamic banking law as they are learned in Conventional banking laws. By sections 250 (1), (2) and (3) of the Constitution and 2 (2) of the Federal High Court Act 2004, the qualification for appointment as a judge of the Federal High Court is solely being a legal practitioner for at least 10 years or being a judge of a court having unlimited jurisdiction in civil or criminal matters in Nigeria or a court having jurisdiction in appeals from any such court in Nigeria. This is in addition to obtaining the requisite academic and legal training in the university and the Nigerian Law School. This requirement is not obtainable in respect to Islamic banking laws as substantive and procedural Islamic law principles are not being taught in most Nigerian Universities and the Nigerian Law School.

It is obvious that judges of the Federal High Court are generally equipped with the requisite knowledge, training and expertise to handle disputes that may arise in the course of conventional banking transaction such as disputes relating to prospectus liability, insolvency, security and guarantee, illegality, fraud, loan/finance, structured finance disputes and contractual interpretations, criminal breach of trust and other criminal practices, disputes relating to the interpretation and application of banking laws and regulations, disputes involving the operations of financial institutions which includes cases related to licensing, registration, and regulation of banks and financial institutions; disputes concerning the winding

up or liquidation of banks; Disputes involving the Monetary Policy Committee (MPC) of the Central Bank of Nigeria and cases of regulatory compliance.

These kinds of disputes may also arise in the course of Islamic banking businesses between an Islamic Bank and other banks or between an Islamic bank and its customer as well as between stakeholders (shareholders) in the bank as the case may be.⁴⁶ These disputes squarely fall within the exclusive jurisdiction and competence of the Federal High Court because, even if the disputes arose between an Islamic bank and others because the disputes arose out of and are governed by Nigerian legislations at which the court is knowledgeable and trained. Therefore, since judges of the Federal High Court are required to be a qualified legal practitioner for at least 10 years, they are presumed to be learned in all ramifications of the banking law in Nigeria.

Specifically, Islamic banks offer products that are not offered by conventional banks and disputes arising from these products require the court to determine the compliance or non-compliance of the transaction to Islamic principles. This may involve questions about the legitimacy of certain investments or the permissibility of certain transactions; profit-sharing in investment accounts or profit-sharing investment contracts; default of loans or failure to fulfill financial obligations; calculation of penalties, or the process of debt collection and recovery; breach of *Musharakah*, *Mudarabah*, *Murabahah*, *Ijarah*, *Bai'as Salam*, *Istisna'* and other related transactions such as Sales Contract (*Aqd Al-Bay*), loan contract (*aqd al-qard*) lease contract (*aqd al-ijar*), partnerships (*al-sharikat*), agency contract (*aqd al-wakalah*), investment contracts, pawning and mortgage (*Al-Rahn*); determining nature of *gharar* and its effect. These disputes are purely governed by the Islamic financial laws at which the judges are neither knowledgeable, trained nor required to be so. Effective resolution of these disputes requires an in-dept and thorough knowledge of the existing substantive Islamic legal rules and principles as well as procedural postulations that are to be used to apply the legal rules in relevant circumstances on the part of the judge.

The principles of *usul-al fiqh* and *Maqasid-al-Sharia* prescribe the standards and requirements every judge must satisfy before he could be competent to preside over any Islamic matter.⁴⁷ He

46 A.O. Sambo & A.B Abdulkadir (2013) *Shari'ah, Constitutional challenges and the Adjudication of Islamic Finance Disptes in Nigeria* Essentials of Islamic Banking and Finance in Nigeria Benchmark Publishers. 120-148

47 A judge must have a strong understanding of Islamic law and its sources, expertise and deep understanding of Islamic legal principles, jurisprudential concepts and methods of interpreting and applying Islamic law.

must be a Muslim, Male of full legal capacity, free, sane, adult, knowledgeable in Islamic Jurisprudence (*Fiqh*), deep understanding of the Quran, Hadith and the legal opinions of renowned islamic jurists, trustworthy and pious; ability to find the law from the primary sources, interpret and apply the law to factual circumstances and ability to conduct an analogy by way of *Qiyas* and a deep understanding of *Maqasid al-Shariah*. However, reverse is the case in Nigeria as judges who do not possess any knowledge or training in Islamic law are saddled with the responsibility for adjudicating over these disputes.

A philosophical reading of the provisions of sections 250 of the Constitution and 2 (2) of the Federal High Court Act 2004 *vis-à-vis* the roles and functions of judges would reveal that the drafters of the said sections did not intend to confer in the Federal High Court any powers, jurisdiction or competence over Islamic banking. If the drafters of the laws intend that judges of the Federal High Court have jurisdiction and competence over Islamic banking, the drafters would have made it a requirement that they be learned in Islamic law as did section 237 (2) of the Constitution with regards to justices of the Court of Appeal being learned in Islamic personal law.

In some jurisdictions⁴⁸ other than Nigeria, the legal systems establish specialized courts and panels of experts who possess expertise in Islamic banking and finance as Shariah advisors to assist judges in understanding and applying Islamic principles in the resolution of disputes and offer expert and well researched legal and jurisprudential opinions on questions bordering on Islamic banking upon which judges when confronted with issues of Islamic banking over which they are not knowledgeable or trained. This is not the case in Nigeria as the judges of the Federal High Court, though not trained in Islamic law, are allowed to administer the law without any provision for legal guidance as to Islamic banking principles which occasions miscarriage of justice.

This work is of the humble position that taking the arguments side by side and in view of the lack of knowledge and/or training over Islamic law, the Federal High Court cannot have and exercise jurisdiction over Islamic banking matters with competence.

48 Like Malasia and Egypt

8. JURISDICTION AND COMPETENCE OF STATES HIGH COURT OVER ISLAMIC BANKING DISPUTES

Sections 255 and 270 of the Constitution, respectively, create the High Court of the FCT, Abuja and High Court for each of the states of the federation. Pursuant to sections 257 (1) and 272 (1) of the Constitution which bestow on the High Court an expansive, unlimited and unrestricted original jurisdiction⁴⁹ to, subject to the provisions of section 251 of the Constitution, hear and determine all manner of claims arising from contractual relationships, commercial agreements, tort and any other sort of civil transactions that may arise out of any relationship between parties including disputes that may arise between a bank and its customer.⁵⁰

As the High Court exercises three kinds of jurisdictions,⁵¹ sections 257 (2) and 272 (2) empower the High Court to supervise and entertain appeals from lower courts as provided for by respective states laws in that regard except for appeals from decisions of an Area Court involving a question of Islamic personal law and Customary law which shall go to the Sharia Court of Appeal and Customary Court of Appeal respectively. Further to the foregoing provisions of the Constitution, the respective laws of individual States also confer original, appellate and supervisory jurisdictions on the State High Courts⁵² exercisable over inferior courts, tribunals, executive or statutory bodies, by way of issuing prerogative orders of certiorari, prohibition, and mandamus amongst others.

Having determined that states and FCT High Courts have concurrent jurisdiction with the Federal High Court over matters bordering on banker-customer relationship such as cases on duty to honor cheques issued by customers, duty of secrecy of customers' accounts, duty of care as regards property deposited by customer, receiving money for customer's account, duty to render statement of account and abide by mandates given by customer, we shall now proceed to look at the qualification and competence of the judges of the High Court to adjudicate over issues of banker-customer relationship in respect of Islamic banking. The cases of Jammal Steel

49 *Madu V Mbakwe* (2017) LPELR -CA/E/379C/2014.

50 *Kayili V Yilbuk & Ors.* (2015) LPELR -SC 92/2005

51 Original jurisdiction in civil and criminal matters, appellate and supervisor jurisdictions over inferior courts or tribunals.

52 For example, section 28 of the High Court Law of Lagos State provides that the Court shall have appellate jurisdiction to hear and determine all appeals from the decisions of Magistrate Courts of the State in civil and criminal matters.

Structures Limited V WEMA Bank Limited⁵³ and FMBN V NDIC 1999 (SCNJ) 57 at 82 are good authorities on this point.

Qualifications for appointment of persons to the office of a judge of the High Court determines the competence of the court over matters that may come before the court. By section 256(2) of the Constitution which is in *pari materia* with section 271(2) of the Constitution, judges of the High Court are appointed by either the President or Governor of a state based on the recommendation of the National Judicial Council after and complying with and fulfilling some certain procedure such as application, recommendation of applicants, tests and screening and eventual selection of qualified applicants.

The requirement for the appointment as High Court judge in Nigeria is provided for sections 256(3), 271(3) of the Constitution and section 5 of the FCT High Court Act to the effect that a person shall not be qualified to hold the office of a Judge of the High Court unless he is qualified to practice as a legal practitioner in Nigeria and has been so qualified for a period of not less than ten years.

From the foregoing provisions, the sole requirement for appointment as a High Court judge is 10 years qualification as a legal practitioner. This is more of a general or omnibus provision pursuant to which other requirements are imposed by other legislations or by regulations of courts. Thus, the Legal Practitioners Act and other statutes place some fundamental requirements which a person must fulfil before he becomes a legal practitioner.

Affirming knowledge of Islamic law as a prerequisite for competence to adjudicate over Islamic banking matters, Rule 4 (4) (i) (a) and (e) of the NJC guidelines for appointment of superior court judges provides that good character and reputation, diligence and hard work, honesty, integrity and sound knowledge of law and consistent adherence to professional ethics are essential requirements for the selection of suitable candidates for the judicial office in any of the superior courts of record in Nigeria so much that lack of any of such qualities renders the candidate unqualified, incompetent and unfit for the appointment because without any of such qualities, he cannot discharge the duties of the exalted office. Therefore, without sound knowledge of the law which is to be interpreted and applied by the judge, the qualification, competence and ability to discharge the duties of the office cannot be attained. Therefore, since judges of States and Federal High Court, are not knowledgeable in Islamic law and are not

53 (1973) 1 All. N.L.R. Part II 208..

required to be so, they lack the qualification, competence and ability to discharge the duties of their offices in respect of Islamic banking matters, hence lack jurisdiction.

The requirement of the Rules that in the case of appointment of a candidate to the office of Kadi of a Sharia Court of Appeal he must have knowledge of Arabic and grammar further buttresses the point that knowledge of the law is essential to competence and jurisdiction.

Looking at the nature of disputes that may arise in Islamic banking transactions and having regard to the constitutionally required qualification and background of the judges occupying the High Court, the question that sought to be answered is, are High Court Judges reasonably and justifiably qualified and competent to decide matters that relate to Islamic banking? With regards to banking disputes purely governed by Nigerian legislations or common law, the High Court could be said to have requisite jurisdiction and competence because the judges are not only knowledgeable but are also trained and learned in the legislations governing such disputes such as banker-customer relationship, issues of unauthorized withdrawals or transfers from customer's account; failure or refusal to honor customer's instructions for withdrawals, transfers or other transactions; disputes as to imposition of fees and service charges; account errors in customer's account balance, statements, or transactions; customer service issues that may have to do with communication, responsiveness, and handling of complaints; breach of confidentiality, disputes over account statements, unauthorized transactions, freezing and seizure of accounts, or disputes arising from electronic banking services, misrepresentation, unfair contract terms, or lack of transparency; fraud and misrepresentation: cases involving fraudulent activities, misrepresentation of financial statements, and other unethical practices in banking transactions.

This class of disputes which may arise in both conventional and Islamic banking transactions are governed by Nigerian legislations and/or common law. Hence, the High court is competent to handle these sorts of cases even if they arose between an Islamic bank and its customer because the law governing these sorts of relationship is the Nigerian banking law at which the judges are learned and trained.

Judges of the High Court may not be competent to preside over disputes that are governed purely by Islamic law because the judge lacks the requisite knowledge and training in Islamic law. Disputes as to the performance or non-performance of *musharakah*,⁵⁴ *mudarabah* and

⁵⁴ Failure or refusal of the *musharik* to pay the agreed returns to the financiers either dishonestly or out of necessity, breach of a term in the Musharakah agreement and the risk of loss in *Musharakah*,

other products of *Ijarah* transactions,⁵⁵ construction and interpretation of the terms of Islamic contracts between an Islamic bank and its customers, disputes between the bank and customer in *Ijara*, disputes as to who bears the consequence of an increment that might have arisen in *Bai' as salam*, *Murabahah* and *Istis'na* transactions, sales contract (*Aqd Al-Bay*), loan contract (*aqd al-qard*), lease contract (*aqd al-ijar*), partnerships (*al-sharikat*), agency contract (*aqd al-wakalah*), investment contracts, pawning and mortgage (*Al-Rahn*). These and other disputes that may arise out of Islamic banking transactions require not only deep knowledge of the Islamic legal rulings but also a good grasp of Arabic language in which most of the legal rulings are prescribed.

These disputes arising out of Islamic banking transactions are founded and based on different legal jurisprudence from the civil law in which the judges are trained. Matters of contracts signed by the parties are not related to the common law types of contracts and although they have some similarities, Islamic contracts are fundamentally different in principles thereby making the construction or interpretation a totally different thing.

It is therefore beyond doubt that interpretation of Islamic contracts is beyond the competence of the judge of a High Court as the judges in these courts are not trained in that respect and allowing the judges to so interpret often occasions miscarriage or misplacement of justice in the courts.

9. CONCLUSION

Disputes arising in the course of Islamic banking may fall within the ambit of Nigerian legislations, Islamic commercial law or combination of the two. While the Federal and States High Courts may have jurisdiction and competence over the former, they may not in respect of the latter because judges of these courts are not knowledgeable in Islamic law and neither the Constitution nor any other law requires them to be so.

This work finds that Islamic banking cases that come before the courts suffer great deal of injustices as a result of misapplication and misinterpretation of the principles of the law and terms of contracts of parties because the judges lack the competence to appreciate and understand the law governing the special transactions and products offered by Islamic banks.

⁵⁵ Such as disputes as to who bears risk among the parties in the event of damage to the subject matter of *Ijarah* and dispute as to the fate of the subject matter of *Ijarah* often arise between the parties if the lessee defaults in paying up his obligations or vice versa; Other disputes are Loss of object of *Ijarah* as a result of factors beyond the control or expectation of the customer as well as loss out of negligence.

The work also finds that since no Nigerian court is expressly clothed with jurisdiction over Islamic banking matters, judges of the Federal and State High Courts lack jurisdiction and competence over Islamic banking matters. The paper recommends a general overhaul of sections 251(1) (d), 261 and 276 of the Constitution to clear the doubts as to the jurisdiction of Federal and States High Courts over Islamic banking matters and expressly confer same in the judges of the Sharia Court of Appeal who are learned and trained in Islamic law. The work also recommends the creation of special courts or Sharia Councils that would be guiding judges on Islamic banking matters.